

Digital Library Practice in Under Graduate Colleges

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Abstract—This paper is intended to understand the necessity of digital libraries to be applied in Under Graduate Colleges. It's been very much important to study this in concern of Indian Undergraduate Courses where digital library plays the role of soul in education filed in the modern technically advanced age. The study carries close study of literature review from some empirical study resources. The fast growing technological advancements in all fields has given a birth to the digital platform for the library feasible and reader's friendly. As a soul of colleges and educational institutes, digital library provides easy learning resources for educational academics advantages over conventional libraries. The present paper closely analyses the best usage/practice of this phenomenon for the undergraduate students in India in the present era.

Keywords- *Digital Library-* A collection of information resources in electronic format

Empirical- Based on Observation *Anxiety-* A feeling of uneasiness

1.1 Introduction and Theoretical Framework:

The present study aims to analyze Digital library, advantages and disadvantages of digital library, use and importance of digital library for the undergraduate students in India.

Before studying digital library it's been very important to discuss about the concept of "anxiety" of undergraduate students towards the traditional libraries is a psychological and describes a fear or unease student's experience in a library. The idea of "library anxiety" has been put in front around since the 1970s. Library anxiety is a commonly observed factor among undergraduate students characterized by feelings of negative emotions, including uneasiness, self-defeating thoughts, fear, tension, physical and mental stress, ruminations and a state of inferiority complex and less skill to find necessary resources. Fraser and Bartlett (2018) argue that undergraduate students often experience discomfort or anxious feelings when interacting with the library and its resources and services and library staff. According to Jiao & Onwuegbuzie (1999) and Onwuegbuzie, Jiao & Bostick (2004), library anxiety occurs in some special circumstances or contexts; therefore, students experience library anxiety is not anxious outside of the library.

To overcome on this "anxiety" the term Digital Library helps. The term 'Digital library' is a collection of digital or electronic objects that books, articles, journals, research papers, multimedia materials, and other types of content along with means for organizing, storing, and retrieving the files and media contained in the library collection. Digital libraries can have vast size and scope which may be maintained and stored by institutions which can be accessed remotely through computer networks like internet. The library is the cardinal and central part of interest in any educational institute. In the colleges (affiliated to Universities) are provided the curriculum by concerned universities according to the needs of the current hour. Due to this many times many colleges fail to update their traditional libraries. While updating this many major issues do arise such as of infrastructure, Finance, Manpower and students habits (techno-savvy) but the truth cannot be denied of the traditional library which is the bridge between the teaching and learning in physical way. The major part to explore is today's students do spend maximum duration on the internet searching for the material required for their study which may not be authentic and students are not ready to sit in the library and read

hour and hour reading the books in chunks. Considering this the digital library plays important role in a way which is provided to students.

1.2 Digital Library Merits & Demerits in Education:

There are many advantages of digital libraries in the current era which are transformative and revolutionary in the process of transforming information to the end with their wealth of digital resources available in the college libraries. This digital libraries offer convenience, accessibility, and efficiency with the authenticity of the information. Students can explore diverse extended materials from their places where they stay or from any place they want to access with the help of internet facility, beyond the physical boundaries and time constraints of physical presence in the traditional libraries. Thus this saves valuable time and effort of the students that they can utilize for other skills gaining. Rather, digital libraries give a scope for knowledge sharing and accessing, which fosters an interconnected homely community of learners and researchers. This is the age of digital libraries, has become evident that they have become essential tools in our pursuit of knowledge, opening up new horizons and expanding the boundaries of new learning.

On the other hand there are certain drawbacks also in concern of undergraduate students that they must know the proper potential and skills for surfing for the information digitally. It's also the thing that the digital formats may limit access to certain resources that are not available in digital form or have not been transformed into digital data. Students if are not aware about the fake data which is also available in immense number digital form may lead them to the failure in getting knowledge.

1.3 Digital Library transformation:

The students cannot acquire knowledge and develop skills only by attending classes in colleges regularly. In addition to this they need access and use the libraries to enhance their knowledge and the learning experiences. Many colleges and universities have been taken initiatives in digitizing their existing libraries to enhance the learning experience of students in a remote and distributed environment which has found to be successful attempt in the knowledge and skill enhancement of students.

Digital library plays an important role for student's educational growth. Librarians play role of educators that procure e-content and give instruction on how to assess and use resources properly. Therefore Librarians required preparing or scrutinizing or providing e-materials which must be relevant, supportive, and useful to the students. This is because the students most of the times cannot find or access the physical material required, in a situations students lose their interest in the physical library. As like the physical library issues some of the factors which impact how students perceive online materials with slow download speed, difficulty reading online due to other technology options such as games, a distraction from social media, and emails. Through the analysis of this it's been necessary make better library experiences with the library and the library's resources, college librarians and teachers can do better in promoting online student learning with e-content emphasize in classrooms or out of classrooms. Students believe in their teachers so they shall start believing the resource cited valuable by them. Wu and Chen (2012) found graduate students often use library resources (e-content) and that college graduate students think that the library resources are important for their course/classwork. E-Library shall provide the e-content resources that explore topics, present information literacy in a new way, or support an assignment can be perceived as valuable to students in their research process on one click.

1.4 Conclusion:

Digital Library is very important as Student perceptions might be influenced by when an online library resource is introduced within a course or program. Graduate students do want access to the online library and content to ensure that they remain updated in the field.

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